

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE USE OF LATIN TERMS IN DRUG NAMES

Karimova Asalkhan

1st year student of the Faculty of Pharmacy of
Samarkand State Medical University

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ABSTRACT: This thesis provides some information about the use of Latin terms in drug names. It is explained with clear analysis through several examples in the use of only Latin terms. In the current modern medicine, there is an opinion about their use in consumption.

KEY WORDS: ituzum, ituzum companions, secretion, function, lunatism, botulism

The Latin language is considered an ancient language and is of great importance in medicine today. We can find it not only in drug names, but also in anatomy and clinical expressions. All these are closely related. That is, all terms are covered by the medical field. It is no exaggeration to say that the Latin language occupies a very important place in medicine. Latin terms have also found their place in other languages. Most of these terms are related to the medical field. It is a relief for representatives of the medical field that the Latin language has found its place in other languages. For speakers of European languages, Latin is considered the language of science.

The Latin language is used a lot in medicine, especially in terms in the field of pharmacology, in the formulation of drug names. The Latin language is very necessary in the naming of drugs and in their prescription. When we describe each medicinal substance and plant, we should pay great attention to its Latin name.

For example, when we name plants, we mean the solanaceae family, here the word "solanaceae" refers to the whole plant family. But each representative of the plant family has an independent name, itzum (solanum), potato (solanum tuberosum) and so on. When we present the composition of medicinal products, we must also fully and correctly reflect the composition of medicinal plants in its composition.

For example: tincture of valerian root - Infusum radices Valerianae. Here we will make a big mistake if we write or do not quote the component of the plant incorrectly. Therefore, manufacturers of medicinal products should be more careful when naming the drug and mentioning its components.

The Latin naming of drug names has also found its place in the prescription. Medical personnel should fully follow the prescription law even

when giving the names of drugs in the prescription. A prescription is a letter from a doctor to a pharmacist in which the pharmacist, as the recipient of the prescription, controls the shikokor. As it can be seen from this, the person who prepares the prescription and the person who provides the medicine to the patient on the basis of it should know the order of writing the prescription thoroughly. With this thought, it should be emphasized that when we describe the names of drugs in the prescription, they should be written in capital letters and in a language that the patient understands.

It is no exaggeration to say that the Latin language has found its place in clinical expressions.

Latin is an ancient language, and the Latin terms used in ancient medicine have been preserved in modern medicine. For example: Tuberculosis - tuberculosis, Leucocytosis - proliferation of cells (leukocytes) in the blood, Botulismus - food poisoning (botula-sausage, kazi), Somnambulismus - sleep walking (lunatism) and so on. Clinical expressions were built on the basis of ancient Greek and Latin languages. Several complex Latin or ancient Greek roots are connected in one word with or without a vowel and translated into Uzbek with several words. For example: Endocrinology is made up of three Greek words and translated into a few words in Uzbek, i.e. "the science of diseases related to the structure and function of internal secretion glands, disorders of these glands".

In conclusion, it should be said that the Latin language is considered an ancient language, and although this language is considered a dead language, it is used almost all over the world. The Latin language covered not only the field of medicine, but also all aspects of science. Latin is the language of science. As we mentioned above, the Latin language has found its place in every field related to medicine. This can be clearly seen in the field of medicine, especially pharmaceuticals, all drugs are named in Latin, which is of great importance in the international distribution of drugs.

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